

Quantitative, Non-Intrusive Imaging of Soot Emission from Aircraft Engines

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Introduction

The development of non-intrusive techniques for the measurement of the exhaust gas flow on aircraft engines is a new challenge for the aviation sector. Very High Bypass Ratio (VHBR) lean burn engines require careful fuel control and optimised staging to minimise non-volatile particulate matter (nvPM) emissions. Variations in fuel flow across injectors will alter the temperature distribution and hence influence nvPM formation and consumption. CIDAR (Combustion species Imaging Diagnostics for Aero-engine Research) supports Rolls-Royce's efforts to develop technologies required for VHBR engines.

Methods

Extractive sampling is the established method for the measurement of exhaust gas and fine particle emissions from various types of aircraft engines under actual operating conditions. Non-intrusive approaches are under development, which do not impact engine performance and require no hardware installed in the exhaust, bypass or entrained flows. CIDAR will further develop (to TRL6: technology demonstrated in relevant industrial environment) the quantitative emissions imaging technologies described in (Wright, 2016). The information these systems will provide is required to deliver reliable VHBR engine performance prediction. The non-intrusive nature of these technologies will allow emissions data to be collected routinely, without affecting the performance of the engine and their improved temporal resolution will potentially enable measurement in both the stationary and transient regimes. These capabilities will allow unprecedented scrutiny of engines' emission behaviour, across a wide range of operating and environmental conditions.

CIDAR will demonstrate cross-sectional imaging of nvPM in exhaust plumes during VHBR engine tests at INTA's jet engine test facility. Laser induced incandescence (LII) based on orthogonal imaging of a light sheet is a well-established tool for the quantification of soot concentrations and distributions in small flames. This configuration is, however, unsuitable for measurements in large engines as it is not possible to achieve the required laser fluence over such a large cross-section, even before the fluence reduction due to plume-induced scattering is considered. Scanned beam LII, with

light collection in the backward direction, has been demonstrated in jet exhaust (Black, 2008 and 2010). CIDAR will use a similarly-scanned excitation beam but in combination with in-plane nearorthogonal collection of the incandescence signal (Figure 1). Cross-sectional images of nvPM concentration will then be produced by combining data acquired from several excitation beam directions. The laser, scanner and camera systems are positioned entirely outside of the flow.

Figure 1. LII system layout at INTA test cell.

Conclusions

The nature of the imaging technique allows a trade-off between spatial and temporal resolution but CIDAR aims to deliver non-intrusive nvPM/soot imaging with 10 cm spatial resolution across a 1.6 m diameter flow, at an SNR-limited rate of up to 1 frame/sec. An LII signal has recently been observed over the nominal beam: plume interaction length (corresponding to the yellow line of Fig. 1), in a VHBR engine at operating conditions, confirming the suitability of the technique for modern, full scale engine tests.

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